

HINDU PHOBIC LEGISLATION: THREAT TO HUMANITARIAN

Debdeep Banerjee

&

Bijayini Namrata Patel

KIIT School of Law, KIIT Deemed to be University

ABSTRACT

Among the hallmark achievements of the modern civilisation is the realisation and dissemination of knowledge that rights to life, liberty and security of persons are primary inherent and inalienable to every human being irrespective of individual's race, nationality, economic status along with manmade discriminations. India, despite of all the diversified cultural fabrics in the preamble the grundnorm pledged to maintain the essence of secularism. Being a secular nation, India has developed personal codified legislations governing the particular religions. The anti-Hindu sentiment which articulates, advances, and amplifies hatred against Hinduism and Hindus is known as Hindu phobia. This write-up attempts to bring out the contemporaneous of the topic and acknowledge the Hindu phobic provisions and legislations in the nation, specifically the Right to Education and Article 30 of our constitution. Lastly it alludes the issue of 'Love Jihad' as a threat to humanitarians along with the stance of India in UN.

Key Words: Secularism, Hinduism, RTE, Art 30, Anti-Hindu.

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Introduction

Hinduism has been represented as a human rights nightmare being the root of all India's crises. The anti-Hindu sentiment which articulates, advances, and amplifies hatred against Hinduism and Hindus is known as Hinduphobia. It is a malignant universal happening that is influenced by past legacies. The unchecked support for and rallying of anti-Hindu sentiments are effective hallmarks of the humanities departments in several universities in the US, Europe, etc. such rampant Hindu phobic sentiments grow under the grab of academic freedom. In particular, western academia is culpable for the growth and evolution of such hatred.

This hate-mongering ideology dates back to the 19th century and has a voluminous history from the colonization of the Indian subcontinent by the British Empire, if not beyond. The cultural edifice of India took a heavy blow during European colonization. The cultural hegemony, economic destruction, and political domination of the colonizers dismantled the moral compass and the self-confidence of the Indians.

The present-day legal system of India tends to mirror the judicial system of our colonizers and thus to this very day regrettably Hinduphobia is widespread in the nation's legal system, such are the ramifications of the historic injustices of the Hinduphobic Nehruvian elite.

The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act,2009

The Right to Education Act (RTE) came into force in 2010. The RTE Act's major goal is to ensure that every child in India, regardless of their economic or caste background, obtains a quality elementary education, which includes children who are forced to drop out. Since then it has been used as a repressive tool by the anti-Hindu forces as it has statistically proven to be highly effective in the reduction of Hindu-run school's market share while tilting the playing field in the favour of Church-run schools. This act places the church in a strategic position allowing it to create a monopoly in the education sector gradually. Under the current legal framework and the legal precedent of 2004 clearly, such a law would be unconstitutional. Even so, the then ruling UPA government overturned a Supreme Court judgment by way of a constitutional amendment in order to enact this legislation. This legislature states that Hindu-run schools must subsidize 25% of seats primarily from the school's own funds. This basically means the financial confiscation of the Hindu schools. The RTE creates multiple burdensome requirements to operate or start schools such as mandatory requirements of a certain amount of

real estate, infrastructure, sports and play equipment, the compulsory establishment of libraries, and setting up school management committees with 75% representation from parents, etc. Thus successfully creating a barrier to the entry and survival of Hindu schools in the already competitive market. The RTE is unconstitutional because it simply does not apply to the minority-run schools shifting the playing field in the favour of church-runs schools. This legislation is a clear violation of constitutional guarantees of freedom of religion and also equal protection of the law given to the Hindus. The result of such unconstitutional legislation is clearly visible. Statistics show that 4160 Hindu-run schools have been closed, 7796 Hindu-run schools have been served closure notices and 11,950 Hindu-run schools face closure threats. As RTE is not applicable to the minority-run institutions we can clearly see that in the market segment of education both majority(Hindu) and minority communities operate on the same material(schools/institutions), and have the same processing procedure (teaching, standards, evaluation), they have the same end product(graduates) yet only one player in this market(minority) is given special privileges.

This is criminal in nature to force schools to shut down in such a nation where education is still a rare find. How will the potential closure of 23,000 schools advance the national interests of a nation?

Article 30 of the Indian constitution

This article upholds the minority community's right to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice. The discussion on article 30 was held during the Second Round table conference in 1931. The clause in the memorandum originally asked for "equal rights for all religions". Whereas, in the joint agreement version, this particular line was left out. Hence, the Indian Christians, schools that had previously received preferential treatment during the colonization of India would still have special status after independence. Article 30 provides similar preferential treatment to religious and linguistic minorities. In the Kerala Education Bill, the judgment by the SC made it clear that Article 30(1) shall allow minorities to start and administer any kind of institution, no limitations were put on the subjects to be taught in such institutions. Hence minorities can start schools, medical colleges, and management institutions. If the religion or language of the management is minority then the institute shall be deemed a minority institution. It shall not be taken into account whether the nature of the institution has any relation to preserving the minority community's religion and/or culture or not. A minority institution can admit from all communities. These institutions do not have any obligation to

admit a fixed percentage of that particular community to qualify as a minority institution; the courts support this view in the case of ‘TMA Pai Foundation v. Others (2002)’¹. As per the Madras High Court order teachers of minority-run schools shall not be bound to take the Teachers Entrance Test(TET) while teachers of majority-run schools have to take the exam. Minority institutions have total autonomy in the selection of teaching staff while state governments have provided detailed legislation mentioning multiple qualifications that are to be followed for the appointment of teaching staff in the case of Majority-run schools. Minority institutions can appoint a teaching staff for a secular subject based on their religious considerations. The same is not allowed for the majority institutions, even if it intends to facilitate and advance religious and cultural education for Hindus. Making it difficult for Hindu schools to teach culture and religion to Hindu children who end up growing up in a cultural void. Article 30(1)² has given minority institutions massive freedom in the appointment of its principal, thus they do not need to consider seniority or merit while appointment. This view is supported by the SC judgment of ‘The Secretary, Malankara Syrian v. T.Jose & Ors(2006)’³ Article 28⁴(no government school can provide any religious education) is not followed in the case of aided minority-run schools and they continue to teach religious principles and practices. At the same time, the same article forbids aided Hindu-run schools to teach religious principles and practices. This answers the questions as to why children tend to have no understanding or appreciation of Indian culture. In case of mismanagement by majority-run institutions, the state can appoint an administrator but the same is not applicable to a minority-run institution. Hence it is difficult to ensure the security of the tenure of teaching staff in minority institutions.

Those who wrote the constitution did not consider the large funding that comes from the multinational Church-based organizations and that the minority community would misuse Article 30 in order to set up massive businesses such as Christian schools, being a part of a global church network, receive foreign donations. Article 30 has given minority institutions unparalleled freedom and rights to set up educational empires and openly support conversion. This article has divided the education system into two sectors one of which is subjected to

¹TMA Pai Foundation v. Others 1994 SCC (2) 734.

² Article 30(1) Indian constitution 1950.

³ The Secretary, Malankara Syrian v. T.Jose & Ors 8599 of 2003 (With CA Nos. 8600/2003 & 8576/2003)

⁴ Article 28, Indian Constitution, 1950.

conversion. It's an insult to their current religious sediments and can be interpreted unconstitutional⁹.

The current Love Jihad plot has its origins in India's 1947 partition. India and Pakistan were born as a result of this division. The formation of two countries with distinct main religions resulted in massive migration, with millions of people migrating between them and widespread claims of sexual predation and forced conversions of women by men of both faiths.

Love jihad has been linked to Hindu nationalism, notably the more extreme strain of Hindutva associated with India. Many right-wing Hindutva parties, like as Vishva Hindu Parishad (VHP), take anti-Islamic positions that are hostile to inter-faith marriage and religious pluralism, which can often lead to mob violence driven by charges of love jihad.

In reaction to the alleged love jihad plot, Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh members have announced the initiation of a Reverse Love Jihad campaign to marry Hindu men to Muslim women. Rape and kidnapping of Muslim women have been recorded in various districts of Uttar Pradesh in connection with the campaign. The perpetrators of these incidents are alleged to be affiliate members who are paid for their activities by the affiliates.

Conclusion

Recently India broke the silence and flagged the hypocrisy of the world at the United Nations (UN) to note. Till date UN recognises the violence and discrimination against 'Abrahamic' religions (Judaism, Christianity, Islam) while the same is not acknowledged for religions with Indian origin such as Hinduism, Buddhism and Sikhism. The primary issue being that Abrahamic religions have difficulty in accepting these religions as valid faith. As per statistics 95% of the entire Hindu population lives in India and Nepal¹⁰ which is the only other nation in the world to have a Hindu majority. While there are 126 nations with Christian majority states of which 16 have declared formally Christianity as a state religion. There are 49 nations with Muslim majority. Hindus often have face problems in such Abrahamic majority nations to recognise acts of crime against them. These statistics clearly show the asymmetry as in how world views Hinduism and any crimes committed against them in Non-Hindu states. Even the atrocities such as bombing of Sikh gurudwaras in Afghanistan, the shattering of the

⁹ Murali KV, *When the Hinduphobic legal system does not draw strength from the letter and the spirit of the law, but contempt*, PGURU (14Apr,2018) [When the Hinduphobic legal system does not draw strength from the letter and the spirit of the law, but contempt - PGurus.](#)

¹⁰ Supra Note 7

Bamiyan Buddha and the exodus of Hindus in the Muslim majority Kashmir during the terror campaign only appears to be a mere event for the rest of the world. India needs to rapidly reform laws and legislations that aim to be secular but are in reality a clear attempt to discriminate against religions having origins in India. Grounds of multiple legislations are to re-examined for their Constitutional validity in order to live up to the word ‘secular state’ in its true meaning. In this modern world India’s stance in the UN signal that India shall no longer follow that consensus that atrocities against Indic religions shall not be spoken about. If one calls out anti-Christian violence or Islamophobia or anti-Semitism, then one should also be able to call out Hinduphobia.

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